

Chemical Constituents of *Clerodendron infortunatum* Linn. and *Ficus racemosa* Linn.

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CLERODENDRON *infortunatum* Linn. (Verbenaceae) is a shrub and found throughout India. All parts of the plant have a bitter pungent taste. The leaves are used externally for tumors and certain skin diseases¹. A perusal of literature revealed that some work has been reported on the roots²⁻⁵ and leaves⁶ of this plant. The present investigation deals with the isolation and identification of the constituents from flowers.

Ficus racemosa Linn. (Moraceae), a moderate sized tree, is an important medicinal plant⁷. The roots⁸ and leaves⁹ of this plant have been earlier investigated. A chemical investigation of the bark and heartwood of the plant has, therefore, been undertaken.

C. infortunatum: The air dried flowers (2 Kg.) were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The extract was concentrated to 100 ml. On cooling and filtration a solid material was obtained (Fraction-A). The filtrate was concentrated to dryness (Fraction-B).

Fraction-A, on column chromatography over deactivated alumina and elution with petroleum ether, gave a solid which on crystallization (pet. ether), furnished colourless needles, C₂₄H₃₄O₇, m.p. 164°. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard and Noller's test. ν_{max}^{KBr} 1730, 1250, 1018, 735 cm⁻¹, etc.; $\delta(CCl_4)$ 0.92(s), 1.92-2.10(d), 2.9-3.0(t), 4.8(s), 5.95-6.06(d) and 6.5(t); M⁺ 434. It was identified as the diterpene clerodin.

Fraction-B, on column chromatography over deactivated alumina, gave two compounds. Elution with petroleum ether yielded a product, which on crystallization from ethyl acetate gave a white solid, C₂₁H₃₄O, m.p. 67°. ν_{max}^{KBr} 1730, 720 cm⁻¹ [doublet, -(CH₂)_n-bending, n > 4]. It was identified as hentriacontane by m.m.p., Co-TLC with an authentic sample.

Further elution with petroleum ether-benzene (4:1), gave a greenish-white solid which on crystallization (pet. ether) gave colourless needles, C₂₃H₃₈O, m.p. 148°. ν_{max}^{KBr} 3400-3200, 1630, 960, 885, 795 cm⁻¹, etc. It was identified as (24s)-ethyl-cholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol by m.m.p. and Co-TLC with an authentic sample.

F. racemosa: The dried and powdered bark (2 Kg.) was extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The extract was concentrated and chromatographed

over deactivated alumina. Elution with petroleum ether and crystallization from methanol gave compound A, C₂₈H₅₂O₂, m.p. 184°. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard, Noller's and TNM tests. ν_{max}^{KBr} 1750, 1450, 1380, 1365, 1240, 975 cm⁻¹, etc. M⁺ 468. Compound A was identified as gluanol acetate.

Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) and benzene and crystallization from methanol gave shining white flakes of compound B, m.p. 136-37°. It was identified as β -sitosterol by m.m.p. and Co-TLC with an authentic sample, and preparation of its acetate, m.p. 127° and benzoate, m.p. 143°.

In addition a small amount of a long chain ketonic compound, m.p. 72° was also isolated.

Heartwood shavings (5 Kg.) were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The pet. ether extract was chromatographed over deactivated alumina. Elution with petroleum ether yielded a product which was identified as gluanol acetate and elution with benzene gave β -sitosterol.

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Potential Antituberculosis Compounds : Part I. Substituted Thioureas Containing Quinoline Nucleus*

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ANTIBACTERIAL property of thiourea was observed by E. Nicholas¹ in 1928 and Mayer in 1941². Sulphanilamido thiourea and phenyl sulphanil-amido thiourea were found to be very active against

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tuberculosis, *in vitro*². A large number of diaryl substituted thioureas have been prepared by various workers^{3,4,5,6} so far and a good number of them were found to be active. It is interesting to find out whether, the replacement of one of the aryl rings by a para substituted quinoline ring does increase the activity or not. Quinoline ring was of interest as 8-alkoxy quinolines and aminoquinolines are generally bacteriostatic^{7,8}.

No.	R	R ¹	M.P.*	** Activity Micrograms per ml
1		-OCH ₃	192°	40.0
2		-OC ₂ H ₅	154°	0.5
3		-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	164°	0.5
4		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	165°	2.0
5	8-ethoxy-5-quinolyl	-OC ₂ H ₅ (n)	170°	0.5
6		-OC ₂ H ₅ (iso)	176°	5.0
7		-CH ₃	198°	10.0
8		-Cl	186°	40.0
9		-N(CH ₃) ₂	193-194°	100.0
10		-H	184°	100.0
11		-OCH ₃	170°	5.0
12		-OC ₂ H ₅	150°	0.5
13		-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	151°	0.2
14		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	160°	1.0
15	8-n-butoxy-5-quinolyl	-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	184°	0.5
16		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	152°	5.0
17		-CH ₃	172°	20.0
18		-Cl	178°	40.0
19		-N(CH ₃) ₂	188°	100.0
20		-H	175°	100.0
21		-OCH ₃	151°	5.0
22		-OC ₂ H ₅	158°	0.5
23		-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	165°	2.0
24		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	178°	2.0
25	8-chloro-5-quinolyl	-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	177°	0.5
26		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	198°	10.0
27		-CH ₃	187°	40.0
28		-Cl	179°	20.0
29		-N(CH ₃) ₂	170°	100.0
30		-H	168°	100.0
31		-OCH ₃	177°	10.0
32		-OC ₂ H ₅	150°	0.5
33		-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	145-146°	2.0
34		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	141°	5.0
35	5-chloro-8-quinolyl	-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	127°	0.5
36		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	138°	5.0
37		-CH ₃	179-180°	5.0
38		-Cl	174° d	100.0
39		-N(CH ₃) ₂	163-164° d	100.0
40		-H	174°	40.0
41		-OCH ₃	146°	5.0
42		-OC ₂ H ₅	161°	0.5
43		-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	146°	0.2
44		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	139-140°	5.0
45	6-quinolyl	-OC ₄ H ₉ (n)	153°	0.5
46		-OC ₄ H ₉ (iso)	133°	2.0
47		-CH ₃	131°	2.0
48		-Cl	158-159°	5.0
49		-N(CH ₃) ₂	168°	100.0
50		-H	163°	40.0

* All the m.p.s. are uncorrected and depend on the speed of heating.

** Micrograms/ml for (i) INH=0.04
(ii) Streptomycin=1.0.

The present communication describes diaryl substituted thioureas in which, one of the aryl ring is substituted by a substituted quinoline ring. These have been prepared by refluxing the substituted aminoquinolines with different aryl isothiocyanates in ethanol. The yields range from 60-80%. All the prepared compounds are new and gave correct elemental analysis. All the compounds were tested *in vitro*. The results of the testing are expressed in minimum inhibitory concentration in micrograms/ml. Compounds having -OC₂H₅, -OC₄H₉(n) and -OC₄H₉(iso) in para position of the phenyl ring were found to be more active.

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Solid State Studies on Polymerization and Depolymerization of Tungstate Ion with Mn(IV) as the Hetero-atom

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A new polymeric compound, Na₄[MnW₁₂O₄₀]·32H₂O, has been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical and molecular weight determinations. The oxidation state of the central manganese(IV) ion has been established by magnetic and e. s. r. data. The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied extensively in solid state.

25 grams of sodium tungstate in water (200 ml) was heated to 90° and a mixed solution of manganese(II) sulphate (5 g.) in water (50 ml) and